

A study on the Determinants of Women Empowerment in Sendurai Taluk of Ariyalur District in Tamil Nadu

A.Saravanan, Ph.D., Research Scholar, PG & Research Department of Economics, Gobi Arts & Science College, Gobichettipalayam-638453, Erode district, Tamil Nadu

Dr.A.Raja, Associate Professor, PG & Research Department of Economics, Gobi Arts & Science College, Gobichettipalayam-638453, Erode district, Tamil Nadu

Abstract

The objective of the study is to identify the factors Determinants of Women Empowerment in Sendurai Taluk of Ariyalur District of Tamil Nadu. The study is confined to a total sample of 423 respondents of each male and female category of the same sampling units, selected from 5 villages of the Sendurai taluk of Ariyalur district. The study concluded that the level of Women Empowerment in the Sendurai taluk of Ariyalur districts is far from satisfactory. The study also highlights the fact that inspite of many Development Programmes initiated by the Government over years, the socio economic institutions that impede women empowerment still has considerable role in the slow progress of women empowerment in the areas. The rural women's access to income earning, access asset ownership, political participation, educational access, attending healthcare needs and exposure to family level decision making etc., are yet to be reached to the stake holders. The status of rural women in these areas even today is treated secondary and no importance has been attached with them. Domestic violence, dowry harassments, female infanticide, wife beating, divorce and mental torture still continues which have a serious cumulative negative consequence on women's health and quality of life.

Keywords: Women, Empowerment, WEI, OLS

1. Introduction

The problem of women development in India has long been baffled the policy makers, administrators and social scientists across the country and the debate is still continuing on the meaning, character and direction of their socio economic transformations. The approaches and mechanisms evolved to empower women in the country; especially in rural areas are yet to yield desirable results because they have been grossly misconceived. The welfare approach conceived in the country so far has failed to deliver the goods because of the prevailing rigid socio-economic stratifications, deep rooted cultural disparities as well as the lack of political will to establish an egalitarian social order. These programmes did not address the underlying structural factors, which failed to distinguish between the 'condition of women' and 'position of women'. Condition is the state in which poor women live viz., low wage, poor nutrition, lack of access to health care, education, training etc., whereas 'position' is the socio and economic status of

women as compared to men in the redistribution of power in areas where it perpetuate male domination. Most of the programmes initiated so far have focused on the daily conditions of women's existence, while their position remains largely unchanged. "The social policy has not evolved in the welfare status within the ideal democratic decision making process of weighing the claims of all against the larger consensus to the direction the society is to take. Group interests with varying degrees of power and influences have succeeded in pressuring the governments at the cost of the lesser privileged groups and individuals.

Though, the Government of India has initiated many schemes aiming for providing better opportunities to women in rural areas; the unwilling effect of these appears to distribute the benefits unevenly. Inequality among different sections of the population particularly between men and women continues. The incidence of unemployment is greater among female than male. The structure of employment opportunities for women relatively remains unchanged. The programmes of the Government of India to create awareness and understanding of the problems at gross root levels through promotion of Mahila Mandals, expansion of functional literacy programmes, expansion of minimum health facilities and improvement in nutrition status, have no doubt, helped the rural women in attaining their desired goals to some extent. But the women in rural areas still fall short in pace with overall development. Their role has not been fully recognized, nor has it been given weightage in their struggle of fighting against poverty, inequality and social justice. Although, education has been viewed as a potential instrument for the empowerment of women in rural areas, it is not an independent variable. Educability of individual women in a group society depends upon several structural variables viz., spatial, socio-economic and socio-cultural in nature. These structural variables play a determinant role either as facilitators or as constraints in the process of diffusion of knowledge on the relevance of equality and social justice. Systematic research at regional levels are therefore, essential to identify the specific structural variables which act as constraints in the empowerment of women in the general society, especially those at the lower rung of the rural social order for policy making. The results of such studies it is hoped would help the policy maker in (i) Comparing the socio, economic conditions / status of women in rural areas across regions in the country, (ii) Effective implementation and monitoring of the progress of existing social policies ensuring

gender equality across regions to evolve a suitable regional planning (if necessary) for uplifting women in rural areas in the country. The study on “the Determinants of Women Empowerment in Sendurai Taluk of Ariyalur District in Tamilnadu” is an attempt on this direction

2. Review of Literatures

Purusottam Nayak et-al (2008) has found that acceptance of unequal gender norms by women are still prevailing in the society. More than half of the women believe wife beating to be justified for one reason or the other. Fewer women have final say on how to spend their earnings. Control over cash earnings increases with age, education and with place of residence. Women’s exposure to media is also less relative to men. Rural women are more prone to domestic violence than that of urban women. A large gender gap exists in political participation too. The study concluded with an observation that access to education and employment were only enabling factors to empowerment, achievement towards the goal however, depends largely on the attitude of the people towards gender equality.

Imran Sharif Chaudhry et-al (2009) has concluded with the statement that the millennium goal of women empowerment can be achieved only when all concerned bodies are worked in cooperation and understanding of factors included in the model. It adds further that empowering women is an important end in itself as it is not only a human right issue but also has the potential to enhance human well being. Empowering women and empowering their status are essential ingredients for realising the full potential of the economic development of the entire society, ensuring sustainable development in the region, the study observed.

3. Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study is to identify the factors Determinants of Women Empowerment in Sendurai Taluk of Ariyalur District of Tamil Nadu.

4. Methodology

4.1. Selection of Sample Households

Ariyalur District forms the universe of the study. Ariyalur district has three taluks viz., Ariyalur, Udayarpalyam and Sendurai, of these Sendurai taluk was selected on purpose on the ground that this taluk has the lowest human development index, highest rural population and has relatively larger but scattered industrial occupations in the district. In order to make the study precise and objective, 5 villages were selected from the taluks at random, giving equal representation to all the villages. A list of households from each selected village was prepared, out of which 423 samples were selected at random. All the women respondents selected for the study were married, found in the age group of 22-70 years. In order to make comparison with men with respect to the gender related and empowerment characters an equal number of men respondents from the same households were interviewed on the basis of a specifically designed schedule. Thus, the study is confined to a total sample of 423 respondents of each male and female category of the same sampling units, selected from 5 villages of the Sendurai taluk of Ariyalur district

4.2. Analytical Tools

4.2.1. Women Empowerment Index

The Women Empowerment Index for each dimension viz., [Personal Autonomy Index (PAUI), Economic Decision Making Index (EDMI), Households Decision Making Index (HDMI) and Political Autonomy Index (POAI)] were constructed by using United Nations Development Programme (UNDP, 2005) formulation on Human Development Index;

$$I_j = \frac{X_{ij} - \text{Min}(X_i)}{\text{Max}(X_i) - \text{Min}(X_i)}$$

Where,

I_j = Dimension Index

X_{ij} = Actual score value

$\text{Min}(X_i)$ = Minimum score value

$\text{Max}(X_i)$ = Maximum score value

For each of these four dimensions, an Equally Distributed Equivalent Percentage (EDEP) is calculated, as a population – weighted average, by using the following formula;

$$EDEP = \left[\frac{\text{Female population shares}}{\text{Female Index}} + \frac{\text{Male population shares}}{\text{Male Index}} \right]^{-1}$$

For political and economic participation and decision-making, the Equally Distributed Equivalent Percentage (EDEP) is then indexed by dividing it by 50. The rationale for this indexation is that in an ideal society, with equal empowerment of sexes, the Gender Empowerment Measure (GEM) variables would equal 50 percent, that is, women's share would equal men's share for each variable. Finally, the Cumulative Women Empowerment Index (CWEI) is calculated as a simple average of the four dimensions indexed EDEPs.

$$CWEI = \frac{PAUI + EDM I + HDEI + POAI}{4}$$

Where,

CWEI = Cumulative Women Empowerment Index

PAUI = Personal Autonomy Index

EDMI = Economic Decision Making Index

HDMI = Households Decision Making Index

POAI = Political Autonomy Index

It is hypothesised that all the indices constructed above have positive relationship with Composite Women Empowerment Index, which is the composite index of the four separate indices. Besides, there are some explanatory variables viz., family type, family size, age, cultural belief, fear of violence, distances of healthcare centres from respondents home, distance of school from respondents home, which are also hypothesised to have negative relationship with the combined Women Empowerment Index.

4.2.2. Determinants of Women Empowerment

In order to estimate the determinants of women empowerment in the sample district, both qualitative (logistic regression) and quantitative (multiple regression) methods of analysis were employed. Qualitative analysis was performed by using logistic model or logistic regression model is an attempt to model the probability of a **yes / success** outcomes using the linear

function of the predictors. In other words, logistic regression is one type of discrete choice model which in general predict categorical dependent variables either binary or multiple.

To add further that the logistic method of estimation is based on logistic curve for all values of the regressors, the value of dependent variables falls between 0 and 1. The probability function is a non-linear function and follows a logistic curve. This is a more realistic pattern of change in the probability compared to other qualitative dependent variable models like the Probit on the ground that the odds ratio which is a measure of the strength and deviation of relationship between the two variables and has a special property as not requiring variables to be normally distributed and 2) a mathematical transformation of the odds ratio is the logit model, and this mathematical transformation removes the problem of asymmetry existing in the odds ratio and in turn make this method superior over other method.

The logistic regression model of incorporating the dependent variables women to be empowered (P_i) is of the following form;

$$P_i = P_i(Y_i = 1) = E(Y_i / X_i) = 1 / (1 + e^{\beta_1 + \beta_2 X_1})$$

Where, if $Y_i=1$, women are empowered and if $Y_i=0$, then the women are not empowered, $E(Y_i/X_i)$ is the expectation that a women is empowered given the value of exogenous variables (X_i), where betas are the parameters to be estimated. Similarly, the probability that the women are not empowered ($1-P_i$) can be estimate as;

$$L_i = \log(P_i / 1 - P_i) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 X_1 + u_i$$

Where, u_i follows the normal distribution with zero mean and variance equal to $1/[N_i P_i (1 - P_i)]$. The exogenous variables are in X_i and N_i denotes the number of respondents and natural logarithmic values were taken both dependent and exogenous variables for estimation.

Since, the purpose of the present analysis is to explore the magnitude of gender gap / empowerment of women in rural areas under the existing social structure in the district, a quantitative multiple regression analyses was also performed. Although, there are various econometric techniques and lot of computational facilities are available for analysis, Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method is still one of the commonly used statistical techniques in estimating the dependency of variables.

The (OLS) is attributed to Carl Friedrich Gauss, a German mathematician and is used in a wide range of economic relationship with family satisfactory results and despite the improvement of computational equipment and statistical information which facilitates the use of other more elaborate econometric technique; OLS is still one of the commonly employed methods in estimating dependence of variables in econometric models. The R-Squared value that lies between 0 and 1 is used for goodness of fit. The observation is when the value is closer to one it indicates the better fit, indication that the percentage of total variation in dependent variables is explained by the independent variables. The regression equations using the OLS method of the following type fitted separately for the composite and taluk level data is of the following;

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \varepsilon$$

Where,

Y = Cumulative Women Empowerment Index (CWEI)

α = Intercept

X₁, X₂, X_n = Independent variables

β₁..... β_n = are the parameters to be estimated

ε = Random unobserved disturbance term, with the mean as zero and the variance as constant

Table-1: List of Selected Variables for Empirical Analysis

Variables	Description of variables	
Dependent Variable		
CWEI	<p align="center">Cumulative Women Empowerment Index = [(PAUI+EDCI+HDMI+POAI)/4]</p> <p>Where, Personal Autonomy Index (PAUI) Economics Domestic Consultation Index (EDCI) Households Decision Making Index (HDMI) Political Autonomy Index (POAI)</p>	
Independent Variables		
FAMILY	Type of family structure	1 = Joint 0 = Nuclear
WORK	Doing any paid work instead of domestic work	1 = Yes 0 = No

ASSET	Respondent having assets	1 = Yes 0 = No
MEDIA	Access to media	1 = Yes 0 = No
POLT	Access to political participation	1 = Yes 0 = No
NOHM	Number of household members	
NOCF	Number of children's in a Family	
AGER	Age of respondent in years	
AGEH	Age of husband in years	
ADBS	Age difference between spouse	
DEPR	Dependency ratio in a household	
EARH	Earner ratio of the household	
EDROH	Earner/dependency ratio of the household	
REDL	Respondent Educational Level (Years)	
SEDL	Spouse Educational Level (Years)	
EDWS	Educational difference with spouse	
LOG-PINH	Natural Logarithm of Per Capita Income of the Household	

The dependent variable (CWEI) included in the model is the Cumulative Women Empowerment Index; while the explanatory variables determines the level of empowerment of women and their expected relationship are; years of women's schooling (REDL), participation in paid work (WORK), access to media, communication and network (MEDIA), natural logarithm of percapita income of the households (LOG-PINH), dependency ratio (DEPR), age of the respondent (AGRE), and asset ownership by the respondent (ASSET) all have positive impact on Cumulative Women Empowerment Index (CWEI), which is also composite index of four separate dimensions indices. On the other hand, there are some independent variables which are hypothesized to have negative impact on CWEP, they are, Joint Family Structure (FAMILY), number of household members (NOHM) and Number of Children's in a Family (NOCR).

The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS Version 15.0) was used to generate percentages and to carry out Bivariate (Cross Tabulation) analysis.

5. Results and Discussion

The study deals about the significant determinants of women empowerment in Sendurai taluk of Ariyalur district in Tamil Nadu based on the primary data collected from 423 respondents selected for this purpose. Although the concept of women empowerment is a multifaceted one and is influenced by many factors, a careful attention was paid on to identify the variables on the basis of the investigators a-priori knowledge on the variables and their relationships with women empowerment in the area. Multicollinearity was performed to identify the inter-correlation between explanatory variables which are largely found insignificant between variables. A complete list of variables included for the construction of women empowerment indices are presented in data description. Both, qualitative and quantitative analyses viz., Logit Regression and Multiple Regression equations using maximum likelihood estimation and Ordinary Least Square methods was fitted to the data to explore the effects of the explanatory variables on women empowerment. Taluk-wise analysis on the determinants of women empowerment were also performed to explore whether there is any significance variations are found in the determinants of women empowerment between taluks.

The logistic model was employed to analyse the determinants of women empowerment where the dependent variable is obtained from the respondents perception that whether they feel empowered or not. If the respondents perceive that she is empowered then the value is assigned to 1 and 0 if otherwise, thereby making the data on women empowerment (dependent variable) qualitative and estimated the impact of the factors that effects women empowerment in the district. Thus, the dependent variable in the Logit regression analysis is the dummy variable, and the various explanatory variables that affect the level of empowerment among women in the district and their relationship with women empowerment are; 1. Family type (FAMILY), 2. Family size (NOHM), 3. Age of the respondent (AGER), 4. Age difference between spouse (ADBS), 5. No. of children in a family (NOCF), 6. Education status (REDL), 7. Educational difference with spouse (EDWS), 8. Dependency ratio (DEPR), 9. Access to Assets (ASSET), 10. Access to media (MEDIA), 11. Access to Political participation (POLT), 12. Log percapita income of the household (LOG-PINH) and the expected relationship between women empowerment and the explanatory variables included in the models are;

1. Higher is the women empowerment when the sample respondent's family is of nuclear type.
2. Higher the family size, lower is the women empowerment; when the respondents age is higher, more is the empowerment. More is the wage difference with spouse less is the women empowerment.
3. Higher the level of education of the respondents higher is the empowerment; higher is the educational gap between respondents and spouses less is the women empowerment.
4. When the dependent ratio is more in the respondent's family less is the empowerment.
5. Greater is the access to asset ownership for respondents greater is the empowerment.
6. When the number of children in a family is less, more is the level of empowerment women.
7. More is the dependent ratio of women respondents lesser is the empowerment.
8. Greater is the women's access to paid work greater is the empowerment.
9. Greater is the women's access to media and communication network greater is the empowerment.

Greater is the political access to women more is the empowerment and greater is the log percapita income of the household, more is the empowerment.

The regression results of the determinants of women empowerment in Sendurai taluk based on the primary sources of data collected from 423 sample women respondents in presented in table-2.

Table –2: Estimated Results of the Explanatory Variables Included in the Logistic and Multiple Regression Analysis: Sendurai Taluk

Explanatory variables	Empowerment Attributes of Qualitative Model		Empowerment Attributes of Quantitative Model		
	Coefficients	Sig.	Coefficients	t	Sig.
(Constant)	.026	.990	.127	2.863	.004
FAMILY	-.686	.060***	-.026	-1.585	.114
NOHM	-.240	.060***	-.004	-2.188	.029**
AGER	.007	.628	.001	.981	.327

A DBS	.052	.244	-.004	-1.970	.050**
NOCF	.009	.943	-.005	-1.087	.278
REDL	-.994	.000*	.022	20.327	.000*
EDWS	.049	.131	-.003	-2.745	.006*
DEPR	2.458	.000*	-.006	-.192	.848
ASSET	-.104	.663	.023	2.424	.016**
MEDIA	.103	.673	.051	5.472	.000*
POLT	-1.442	.000*	.052	5.102	.000*
LOG-PINH	.187	.313	.002	1.584	.114
R ²	.368		.665		
Chi-square	135.152	.000*			
Adjusted R ²			.654		
F			61.837		0.000*
N	423		423		

* Significant at 1 % level, ** Significant at 5 % level, *** Significant at 10 % level

From table-2, it is observed that the fitted regression equations viz., logit and multiple regression models is statistically significant according to the perception made in the study and explained 36 percent and 66 percent of variations respectively in women empowerment is due to the explanatory variables and depicts a goodness of fit. All the partial regression co-efficients estimated for the study have registered with the expected signs. The negative signs registered for the explanatory variables viz., family type, family size, number of households members, age difference with spouse, educational difference with spouse, no. of children and dependency ratio are indicative of the fact that the relationship of these variables with women empowerment is negative and statistically significant at 1 percent level and 5 percent level. The family type, numbers of children's in a family and dependency ratio are indicative of the fact that the relationship of these variables with women empowerment is negative and statistically insignificant. The positive signs registered for the variables viz., age of the respondent, respondent education, ownership access to assets, access to media and communication network,

access to political participation and log percapita income of the households are indicative of their positive relationship with women empowerment, leading to the conclusion that women empowerment is a multifaceted process which needs appropriate policy attention from the agencies involved in the process of women empowerment in the district. Contrary to our perception that number of children in a family has negative relationship with women empowerment, the explanatory variables for Sendurai has registered positive sign, which might be due to the fact that the average number of children below the age of 6 years might be relatively very lower in the taluk.

6. Conclusion

Based on the empirical results and discussion it was concluded that the level of Women Empowerment in the Sendurai taluk of Ariyalur districts is far from satisfactory. The study also highlights the fact that inspite of many Development Programmes initiated by the Government over years, the socio economic institutions that impede women empowerment still has considerable role in the slow progress of women empowerment in the areas. The rural women's access to income earning, access asset ownership, political participation, educational access, attending healthcare needs and exposure to family level decision making etc., are yet to be reached to the stake holders. The status of rural women in these areas even today is treated secondary and no importance has been attached with them. Domestic violence, dowry harassments, female infanticide, wife beating, divorce and mental torture still continues which have a serious cumulative negative consequence on women's health and quality of life.

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